

Tensile Behavior of Half Grouted Sleeve Connections: Experimental Study and Analytical Modeling

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Abstract. Half grouted sleeve connections, consisting of a threaded end and a grouted sleeve end, are a convenient and economical solution in joining rebars together in precast concrete construction. In order to study the tensile properties of this connection, 15 half grouted sleeve splices for steel bars were tested under static tensile load. The main parameters of the experimental research are bar diameter, sleeve dimensions and rebar offset. The tests show that the specimens exhibit three categories of failure, namely rebar tension fracture, rebar pull out due to bond failure, and thread shear failure. Rebar offset due to construction error has a negligible influence on the load carrying capacity of the specimen. An analytical model is established to calculate the tensile capacity of the specimens with bond failure considering the confinement effect of the sleeve. Satisfactory agreements are made between the predictions and test results. The issues leading to thread failure are discussed. A design method is proposed to prevent specimens from premature thread failure.

Key word half grout sleeve connection; failure mode; bearing capacity; strain; analytical model

1 Introduction

Grouted sleeve connections are widely used in precast concrete construction for joining rebar at precast joints [1-4]. Fig 1 shows typical details for a vertically-connected precast concrete wall structure using grouted sleeve connections [5]. A number of sleeves are embedded at the bottom of an upper precast wall panel. The distance of sleeves is determined by design requirements. Usually the aim of design is to ensure that the sleeve connection have the same performance as cast-in-situ connection. When the sleeves are placed onto the ribbed rebar protruding from

the top of the lower precast wall panel, they are filled with high-strength and low-shrinkage grout. At the time the grout attains its specified strength, a strong bond will develop through interaction among the sleeve, grout and rebar. **When the wall panel is subjected to horizontal load, like wind and seismic load, the overturning moment at the bottom section will result in tension and compression at the opposite sides of the section. The main function of the grouted sleeve connections is to resist tension induced by the horizontal load.**

Fig 1 Grouted sleeve connections used in precast concrete wall

Two types of grouted sleeve connections are typically used. They are full grouted sleeve connection and half grouted sleeve connection. A full grouted sleeve connection has grouted sleeve joints at both ends so that two bars are grouted into the coupler to form the connection. Full grouted sleeve connection reduces the connection length comparing to lapped connection because of the confinement effect of sleeve [6-8]. It also reduces the precision required during construction because the inner diameter of the sleeve is large enough to accommodate moderate construction errors. The behavior of full grouted sleeve connection has been studied by a number of researchers. The idea of grouted sleeve connection came from the observation that confinement in concrete increases bond strength of rebar [9-11]. In 1995, Einea et al. used grouted pipes to join steel bars. He studied the tensile behavior of reinforcing bar splice using grout-filled standard steel pipe and spirally confined lap splices of deformed steel bars [12, 13]. He concluded that the confinement effect provided by the pipe could result in significant reduction of the required lap length. Zhao et al. tested grouted sleeve connections under high temperature. They found that the ultimate load decreases linearly with temperature difference between outer and inner tubes increases [14]. Belleri et al. investigated the seismic behavior of grouted sleeve connections. They concluded that grouted sleeves ensure seismic performance similar to those of traditional connections [15]. Ling et al. conducted a number of studies on tensile behavior of grouted splice connector [16-18]. Ameli et al. tested 3 column-to-cap beam joints connected by half grouted sleeve connections. They concluded that the joints are expected to perform well in moderate to high seismic regions [19]. Sayadi studied the bond behavior of splice sleeves by flexural tests of beams and tensile tests of connections. The results showed that increasing the confinement in elastic length of sleeve caused reduction in bond strength [20, 21]. Henin and Morcoux introduced a non-proprietary bar splice sleeve that is economical and easy to produce [22]. Their test results indicated that the proposed bar splice sleeve satisfies the design requirement to fully develop connecting bars. Seo proposed a head-splice-sleeve and explored its bond strength by static tests [23]. They

recommended that a suitable diameter ratio between head and bar is 1.3 for the design purpose. Hosseini and Rahman studied in the bond behavior of grouted spiral connection [24]. The influence of spiral confinement is highlighted. They founded that the spiral diameter provides more dominant confinement effect than spiral pitch distance in increasing the bond strength.

Half grouted sleeve connection, namely threaded and grouted sleeve connection, has a threaded joint at one end, usually embedded in a precast component, and a grouted sleeve connection at the other end. The schematic of half grout sleeve connection is illustrated in Fig 2. Half grouted sleeve connection has a number of advantages over fully grouted connections. It requires a shorter connection length because the length of a threaded connection is typically less than two times the diameter of the rebar, while the length of a grouted sleeve connection usually requires six to eight times the diameter of the rebar. Half grouted sleeve connections allow for increased precast construction times because the installation of the threaded connection is easy. It also reduces construction error since the threaded joint embedded in a precast component can be placed with a high precision.

Despite its advantages, the behavior of half grouted sleeve connection has not been fully addressed in the literature. And the effect of rebar offset due to construction error has rarely been studied. This paper presents an experimental research program on the tensile behavior of half grouted sleeve connection. Two parameters are examined in the test. They are the diameter of the connecting rebar and the offset of the protruded rebar from the center line of the sleeve. The performance of the connections is assessed by a criterion based on ACI-318 [25] and JGJ 355 [26]. An analytical model is developed to predict the tensile capacity of half grouted connections considering the confinement effect of the sleeve. Some design suggestions are made for the design of half grouted sleeve connections.

2 Test program

Four sizes of half grout sleeve are tested in this research. They are used for rebar diameters of 14mm, 18mm, 22mm and 25mm, respectively. Details of the half grout sleeve

connections are shown in Fig 2. The sleeve is made of ductile iron [27] with a tensile strength of 610 MPa. The dimensions of the sleeve are listed in Table 1. In precast concrete construction, a rebar with a straight thread end [28] is screwed into the threaded end of the sleeve at first. The grout hole and the vent hole are connected to corrugated hoses extending to the surface of the panel for the later grouting. Then the rebar and sleeve are cast into the bottom of a precast wall panel. When the protruded rebar from a lower precast wall is inserted into the sleeve on the upper panel, grout is filled into the sleeve from the grout hole by a grout pump. If grout outflows from the vent hole, pumping is stopped and the sleeve is assumed to be fully filled with grout. Then the grout hole and the vent hole are sealed with a foam plug for protection.

Fifteen specimens are tested with two parameters being studied. One parameter is the diameter of rebar ranging from 14mm to 25mm which are commonly used in practice. The other is the offset of protruding rebar from the center line of the sleeve to account for the effect of construction error, as shown in Fig 3. Wood formwork are constructed to assure the rebar to be positioned accurately in the grout sleeves, which also permit the stability of the specimens during the curing process. Threaded bars are installed in the sleeves by a pipe wrench. Then a torque wrench is used to check that the values of torque are no less than 100Nm and 200Nm for GS14 and GS18, respectively. For GS22 and GS25, the minimum value of torque is 260Nm. Table 1 summarizes the details of the specimens.

Fig 2 Details of half grouted sleeve connection

Table 1 Details of specimens (mm)

specimens	d	L	L1	L2	D	D ₀	t	h	offset
GS14-1,2,3	14	140	24	100	38	26	4	2	0
GS18-1,2,3									0
GS18-4									2
GS18-5	18	160	28	117	44	30	4	2	4
GS18-6									6
GS22-1,2,3	22	195	32	148	48	34	5	2	0
GS25-1,2,3	25	238	35	190	53	37	6	2	0

Fig 3 Rebar offset

Low-shrinkage grout is used as bonding material in the sleeve. The compressive strength of the grout is 44.5MPa. The nominal yield strength of the rebar is 400MPa. The measured material properties of the rebar are listed in Table 2.

Three strain gauges are mounted on each specimen, as shown in Fig 4. S1 is installed on protruding rebar at about 20mm from the end of the sleeve to measure the longitudinal strains of the rebar. S2 is placed longitudinally on the sleeve at the mid-length of the sleeve to measure the longitudinal elongation of the sleeve. S3 is installed transversely on the sleeve at the mid-length of the bonded rebar to measure the circumferential expansion of the sleeve due to confinement. The strains are recorded by the static data acquisition instrument TDS-530.

Table 2 Material properties of rebars

Diameter /mm	f_y /MPa	f_u /MPa	Elongation (%)
14	470	622	20.2
18	454	632	16.7
22	439	628	17.9
25	459	618	18.4

Fig 4 Strain Gauges

The tests are conducted by the electro-hydraulic servo material testing machine. The test setup is illustrated in Fig 5. All specimens are loaded with a tensile speed of 0.5kN/s. The loading is force-controlled before yielding. Then it is displacement-controlled with each loading step of 2mm to capture the ultimate load. The force and displacement of the actuator are recorded by the electric-hydraulic loading system.

Fig 5 Test setup

3 Test results

Three failure modes are observed in the test, as shown in Fig 7. They are rebar rupture, bond-slip failure within the sleeve, and thread failure. The location of the rupture is either at the end of a thread or in the middle segment of the rebar after yielding. The rebar fracture happened in the specimens with rebar diameters of 14mm and 18mm. While the specimens with a rebar diameter of 22mm ended with bond failure. Thread failure took place for the specimens with a rebar diameter of 25mm. All of the specimens yielded before failure except for GS25-2. In comparison with the specimens with other two types of failure, the specimens with the failure mode of rebar fracture offer the highest degree of strength and ductility.

The measured force-displacement (P-Δ) curves are shown in Fig 8. The displacement of the clamp was measured. The distance between the two clamps is 500mm. An elastic-plastic response can be observed for all specimens except for GS25-2. The maximum resistance increases remarkably with the increase of rebar diameter. The tensile capacity of the grout sleeve connections with half thread end is governed by (a) the tensile capacity of the rebar, (b) the bond strength between the rebar and the grout, and (c) the tensile capacity of the thread connection,

whichever is the weakest.

The effect of rebar offset is shown in Fig 9. The tensile capacity of the specimen remain nearly unchanged with the increase of rebar offset. The maximum decrease is less than 5% with rebar offset from 0 to 6mm, which is negligible in practice. As we know, the rebar offset will affect the interaction among the rebar, the grout and the sleeve. A larger rebar offset may lead to weaker confinement condition in the grout, which will result in less bond strength. In the test, all specimens with rebar offset had the same failure mode of rebar fracture. Thus, the reduced bond strength resulted from rebar offset cannot be observed. And the effect of rebar offset becomes insignificant.

Normalized stress-strain responses of the rebar and sleeve are illustrated in Fig 10. The normalized strain is equal to the measured strain divided by yield strain of

rebar. The normalized stress is equal to the calculated stress divided by yield stress of rebar. The calculated stress is obtained by dividing the load with the area of the rebar. A linearly decreased strain in circumferential direction is recorded at the early stage because of Poisson effect caused by longitudinal elongation of the sleeve under tensile load. At a higher-load stage, the circumferential strain of the sleeve begins to increase because of the dilation of grout caused by bond slip between the grout and the rebar, which leads to expansion of sleeve in circumferential direction. Meanwhile, the rebar starts to yield, which causes a very slow increase of the longitudinal stress in the sleeve. Thus, the circumferential strain becomes significant compared to longitudinal strain in the sleeve, which causes the longitudinal strain reduces with the increase of circumferential strain in the sleeve due to Poisson effect.

Fig 6 Failure modes

Fig 7 Force versus displacement curves

Fig 8 Effect of rebar offset

(a) GS14-2

(b) GS18-2

(c) GS22-3

(d) GS25-1

Fig 9 Normalized stress-strain responses of the sleeve and rebar

4 Performance assessment

In order to evaluate the performance of half gouted sleeve connections, Ling [18] proposed strength ratio R_s ,

yield ratio R_y and ductility ratio R_d as follows:

$$R_s = \frac{f_u}{f_{sy}} \quad (1)$$

$$R_y = \frac{f_u}{f_{sy}} \quad (2)$$

$$R_d = \frac{\delta_u}{\delta_y} \quad (3)$$

where f_u is the ultimate tensile strength of the connection calculated by the maximum tensile resistance divided by sectional area of rebar, f_{sy} is the specified yield stress of rebar, f_y is the yield stress of the connection, δ_u and δ_y are ultimate and yield displacements, respectively.

According to ACI-318 [25] and JGJ 355 [26], the ultimate tensile strength of the connection should be no less than 1.25 times the specified yield stress of rebar. The

yield ratio and ductility ratio of grouted sleeve connection should be greater than 1.0 and 4.0, respectively. Ameli et al. suggested that the precast concrete specimens with the grouted sleeves having a failure mode of bar fracture can achieve a more ductile behavior than the specimens with the sleeves having a failure of bond failure [4, 19]. Thus, the acceptable failure mode of the sleeves should be rebar fracture to satisfy the requirement of ductile connection in moderate-to-high seismic region. The results of performance assessment are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 Performance assessment of specimens

Specimen	Yield load /kN	Maximum load /kN	Yield ratio (R_y)	Ductility ratio (R_d)	Strength ratio (R_s)	Failure mode*	Remarks
GS14-1	72.5	96	1.31	7.62	1.78	F	Acceptable
GS14-2	72.4	95.7	1.31	5.75	1.84	F	Acceptable
GS14-3	85.0	108.7	1.53	5.71	1.84	F	Acceptable
GS18-1	115.0	160.4	1.31	6.13	1.80	F	Acceptable
GS18-2	119.1	160.2	1.31	4.12	1.80	F	Acceptable
GS18-3	115.5	161.3	1.32	4.13	1.81	F	Acceptable
GS18-4	117.8	165.5	1.33	4.67	1.72	F	Acceptable
GS18-5	113.5	164.1	1.30	4.98	1.83	F	Acceptable
GS18-6	112.5	154.4	1.28	5.29	1.84	F	Acceptable
GS22-1	175.2	229.1	1.28	4.14	1.70	B	Not Acceptable
GS22-2	164.2	229.7	1.20	5.68	1.70	B	Not Acceptable
GS22-3	167.3	230.3	1.22	3.73	1.71	B	Not Acceptable
GS25-1	224.3	287.9	1.27	3.36	1.63	T	Not Acceptable
GS25-2	182.5	182.5	1.03	1.00	1.03	T	Not Acceptable
GS25-3	217.0	270.3	1.23	3.29	1.53	T	Not Acceptable

*Failure mode F, B and T represent bar fracture, bond failure and thread failure, respectively.

5 Analytical model

To study the bond resistance of the grouted sleeve, an analytical model is set up in this section. It is generally believed that confined stress in grout plays an important role in the bond strength between the rebar and grout in grouted sleeve connections [29-31]. Assuming that the confinement stress induced by the sleeve is equally distributed along the length of the sleeve, confined stress in the grout f_{co} can be obtained using the equilibrium

condition, as shown in Fig 11.

$$f_{co}D_0L_2 = 2T_{sl} \quad (4)$$

where D_0 is the inner diameter of the sleeve, L_2 is the bonded length of the rebar, as shown in Fig 2, and T_{sl} is the tensile force in the sleeve.

According to strain records during the test, the maximum strain in the sleeves is less than 1000 $\mu\epsilon$. Thus a linear elastic stress-strain relationship is used for the sleeve. T_{sl} can be expressed as

$$T_{sl} = E_{sl}\epsilon_{sl}f_{sl}L_2 \quad (5)$$

where E_{sl} and t_{sl} are elastic modulus and thickness of the sleeve, respectively. ε_{sl} is circumferential strain measured from the test.

Substitute Eq. (5) into Eq. (4), the confined stress f_{co} can

be written as

$$f_{co} = 2E_{sl}\varepsilon_{sl}t_{sl} / D_0 \quad (6)$$

Fig 10 Equilibrium relationship of the grouted splice

Untrauer [11] suggested a linear formula to calculate the bond strength τ_u between the rebar and concrete with confined stress, which is expressed as

$$\frac{\tau_u}{\sqrt{f_g}} = \alpha\sqrt{f_{co}} + \beta \quad (7)$$

where f_g is compressive strength of grout, α and β are coefficients obtained from test results. By regression analysis, α and β are 0.033 and 3.326, respectively, as shown in Fig 12.

Fig 11 Regression analysis of bond strength τ_u

The tensile capacity of the grouted sleeve connection is the smaller between the bond resistance and the fracture capacity of the rebar, which can be express as

$$P_{u,b} = \tau_u \pi d L_2 \quad (8a)$$

$$P_{u,f} = f_u \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \quad (8b)$$

where $P_{u,b}$ and $P_{u,f}$ are the capacity for bond failure and rebar fracture, respectively, f_u is ultimate tensile strength of the rebar. Substitute Eq. (7) and the values of α and β into Eq. (8), we get

$$P_{u,b} = \pi d L_2 \sqrt{f_g} (0.033\sqrt{f_{co}} + 3.326) \quad (9a)$$

$$P_{u,f} = f_u \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \quad (9b)$$

The actual P_u is the smaller one calculated from Eq. (9a) and Eq. (9b). Table 4 lists the predictions of the formula and the results obtained from the test. Satisfactory agreement is achieved, which showed the accuracy of the proposed formula. However, it should be noted that the predicted failure mode of the 18mm specimens does not match the failure mode of the test. The main reason is that the test data for specimens with bond failure is rare. We assume the capacity of specimens with rebar fracture is the same as the capacity of specimens with bond failure to conduct the regression analysis. Despite this, the predicted results calculated from Eq. (9a) and Eq. (9b). are close to each other for specimens with a rebar diameter of 18mm.

The maximum error is 7%, which is acceptable in terms of accuracy. Further experimental research need to be conducted to obtain a more reliable regression formula.

Table 4 Comparison between predictions and test results

Specimen	$P_{u,test}$ /kN	$P_{u,pre}$ /kN	Predicted failure mode	$P_{u,pre}/P_{u,test}$
GS14-1	96.0	95.7	F	1.00
GS14-2	95.7	95.7	F	1.00
GS14-3	108.7	95.7	F	0.88
GS18-1	160.4	149.7	B*	0.93
GS18-2	160.2	150.8	B*	0.94
GS18-3	161.3	150.8	B*	0.93
GS18-4	165.5	149.6	B*	0.90
GS18-5	164.1	150.6	B*	0.92
GS18-6	154.4	150.2	B*	0.97
GS22-1	229.1	238.7	B	1.04
GS22-2	229.7	236.7	B	1.03
GS22-3	230.3	237.3	B	1.03
MEAN				0.97
COV				0.05

*Predicted failure mode does not match tested failure mode

6 Discussion

The specimens with a rebar diameter of 25mm experienced thread failure. The specimen GS25-1 and GS25-3 yielded before failure. However, the specimen GS25-2 failed in the elastic stage, which resulted in a considerably lower resistance than that of the other two specimens. The ratio of thread engagement length to bar diameter is generally used to avoid thread failure in the fabrication of fasten connections. According to Machinery's Handbook [32], the design thread engagement length can be calculated as

$$L_e = \frac{2A_t}{\pi K_{n,max} \left[\frac{1}{2} + 0.57735n(E_{s,min} - K_{n,max}) \right]} \quad (10)$$

where L_e = length of engagement, A_t = tensile-stress area of the screw thread; n = number of threads per inch; $K_{n,max}$ = maximum minor diameter of internal thread; $E_{s,min}$ = minimum pitch diameter. It is assumed in Eq. (10) that the area of the screw in shear must be twice the tensile-stress area to attain the full strength.

According to the basic dimensions of screw thread

specified in China [33], the maximum minor diameter of internal thread $K_{n,max}$ and minimum pitch diameter $E_{s,min}$ are expressed as

$$E_{s,min} = d - 2 \times \frac{3}{8} H = d - 0.6495p \quad (11)$$

$$K_{n,max} = d - 2 \times \frac{5}{8} H = d - 1.0825p \quad (12)$$

where p is the thread pitch, H is the height of fundamental triangle. The theoretical profile of the thread is shown in Fig 13. For specimen GS-25, p is equal to 3mm. Substituting d and p to Eqs. (10)-(12), we obtain a design engagement length L_e of 19.2mm or 0.77d.

Fig 12 Theoretic profile of thread

Fig 14 shows the ratio of thread length to rebar diameter for each size of sleeve. The actual L_1/d ratio is greater than the theoretic one for all specimens. However, only specimens with rebar diameters of 14mm and 18mm have the acceptable failure mode of rebar fracture. The specimens with a rebar diameter of 25mm has the smallest L_1/d ratio, which is higher than the theoretic one. Yet, a failure in the thread still take place. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fabrication method used in creating the threaded end section of the bar. The approach creates imperfections in the thread which can compromise the strength. So based on the test results, a minimum L_1/d ratio of 1.5 is recommended to avoid thread failure for the sleeves.

Fig 13 L1/d of the half grouted sleeve

Also, we can calculate the minimum bond length $L2_{min}$ for the grout end of the sleeve to avoid bond failure using the following equation:

$$L2_{min} = \frac{P_{u,f}}{\tau_u \pi d} \quad (13)$$

where $p_{u,f}$ is the ultimate load for rebar fracture, which is computed from Eq. (9)b, τ_u is the bond strength between the spliced rebar and the grout, which can be obtained from Eq. (7). Substitute Eq. (7) and Eq. (9) into Eq. (13), we get

$$L2_{min} = \frac{f_u}{4\tau_u} d \quad (14)$$

The calculated bond length $L2_{min}$ is compared with the tested one $L2_{test}$, as shown in Fig 15. The actual bond length is greater than the calculated minimum bond length for specimens with a rebar diameter of 14mm and 25mm, respectively. Therefore, bond failure is not occurred at these specimens. The tested bond length is less than the calculated one for specimens with a rebar diameter of 22mm and rebar pullout takes place in these specimens. The only exception is the specimen with a rebar diameter of 18mm, whose failure mode is rebar fracture even the tested bond length is less than the predicted one. This may be attributed to the assumption of the regression analysis that the capacity of rebar fracture is the same as the capacity of bond failure, as stated in section 5 of this paper.

Fig 14 Bond length L2 of the half grouted sleeve

7 Conclusion

This paper introduces a half grouted sleeve connection. Tensile behavior of the half grouted sleeve connections is tested and assessed. An analytical model is established to predict the ultimate capacity of the connections. The main conclusions are as follows

- 1) Three types of failure mode are observed in the test. They are rebar fracture, bond failure and thread failure. The tensile capacity of the grout sleeve connections with half thread end is governed by (a) the tensile capacity of the rebar, (b) the bond capacity between the rebar and the grout, and (c) the tensile capacity of the thread connection, whichever is the weakest.
- 2) Rebar offset due to construction error has a negligible influence on the load carrying capacity of the specimen because the failure mode is rebar fracture.
- 3) Simplified analytical model is proposed to calculate the load carrying capacity of specimens with bond failure considering the confinement effect of the sleeve. The predictions of the analytical model fit well the experimental results, which demonstrate the accuracy of the proposed method.
- 4) Design requirements are recommended for the thread engagement length and the bond length of the rebar to avoid thread failure and bond failure of the half grouted sleeve connections.

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